

THE RELATION BETWEEN COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE AND INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE

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Abstract: Intercultural competence is a communicative competence using language as a tool for communicating. Indeed, the languages used in communication can be verbal or nonverbal. If the language is essential in our daily communication, it is claimed that the non-verbal predominates our communication.

Key words: intercultural, non-verbal, competence, communicative.

Introduction

Intercultural competence is a communicative competence the use of language as a device for communicating. Indeed, the languages utilized in conversation may be verbal or nonverbal. If the language is crucial in our day by day verbal exchange, it's far claimed that the non-verbal predominates our communicate. Ting-Toomey confirms that : “To be intercultural communicators we want the expertise of each verbal and nonverbal communicate in order to talk sensitively throughout cultural and ethnic boundaries”[39,113]. The validity of the pedagogic version primarily based totally at the local speaker-primarily based totally perception of communicative competence. With its standardized local speaker norms, the version is determined to be utopian, unrealistic, and constraining on the subject of English as an International Language (EIL). It is utopian now no longer handiest due to the fact local speakership is a linguistic myth, however also as it portrays a monolithic notion of the local speaker’s language and culture, through referring mainly to mainstream approaches of wondering and behaving.

It is unrealistic as it fails to mirror the lingua franca reputation of English. It is constraining in that it circumscribes each instructor and learner autonomy via way of means of associating the idea of authenticity with the social milieu of the local speaker.. A new belief of communicative competence is needed, one that recognizes English as a global language. This might embody nearby and international contexts as settings of language use, contain local–nonnative and nonnative–nonnative discourse participants, and take as pedagogic models a success bilinguals with intercultural insights and know-how. As such, it could purpose at the belief intercultural communicative competence in ELT. Although there had been reformulations of the different additives of understanding that underlie Canale and Swain’s influential version of communicative competence, the version—in its barely changed shape via way of means of Canale —nevertheless paperwork the traditional framework for curriculum layout and study room exercise related to communicative language coaching in lots of an academic context. The perception of communicative competence defined withinside the version entails 4 competencies, which can be generally called grammatical competence, sociolinguistic competence, discourse competence, and strategic competence. The first and fundamental is grammatical or formal competence, which refers back to the Chomsky an idea of linguistic competence; it's far the local speaker’s expertise of the syntactic, lexical, morphological, and phonological capabilities of the language, in addition to the ability to control those functions to supply well-shaped phrases and sentences. It offers the linguistic foundation for the policies of utilization which typically bring about accuracy in performance

The first goal of getting to know a overseas language is the manipulation of the language beneath study, however gaining knowledge of the linguistic competence isn't always enough for the learner of a overseas language, as it does now no longer allow him to talk accurately with human beings of other cultures. Learning a

language, then it's miles to get in contact with a brand new tradition. According to Byram and Morgan, "Learners are "committed" to their culture and to deny something within their own being" [12,43].Cultural mastering includes that the learner assimilates factors of a distinct subculture, language and components influencing behavior. We can not separate language from subculture, The studying of lifestyle have to be incorporated into the studying of the language, and move past the extent of "civilization", "Landeskunde" to cope with the deeper and the very massive a part of the iceberg that is hard to look and grasp (conversation style, and factors such structures of values or beliefs, and worldview, If the language affects how we behave and understand things, subculture is likewise inherent withinside the language itself, its structure, its vocabulary, expressions, and may be taught currently with the language. For this reason, Kramersch observes that: "Culture in language learning is not an expendable fifth skill, tacked on, so to speak, to the teaching of speaking, listening,reading, and writing.It is usually withinside the background, proper from day one, prepared to unsettle the coolest language rookies after they assume it least, making obtrusive the obstacles in their hard-received communicative competence, tough their capacity to make feel of the sector round them" [25,1]. Communicative Competence Hymes, via defining communicative competence, he desired to make importance for the social context as he desired to factor out the attention for the "appropriateness" or the sociocultural really well worth of utterances in any given context. Canale and Swain defined the factors of ommunicative competence as consisting of linguistic competence, discourse competence, strategic competence and sociolinguistic competence. While Van Ek he built his new version with the aid of using including more additives to the above listing which can be the socio-cultural competence, or the cappotential to feature in numerous cultures, and the social competence, because of this that familiarity with variations in social customs, similarly to constructing confidence, empathy, and motivation to speak with other

According to the American researcher Mehrabian, the behavioral equation for verbal and nonverbal indicates the outcomes and results of paralanguage on communicate to a more extent : Mehrabian evaluated our verbal exchange and gave the subsequent outcomes: 7% for words, 38% for paralanguage and 55% for non-verbal verbal exchange. This way that the manner we behave in the use of gestures and facial expressions are all companies of messages as language, if it does now no longer more. Since there are variations withinside the languages, there are as much in non-verbal verbal exchange in exceptional cultures: there can also extrade the code from one organization to the opposite and provide upward thrust to misunderstandings or even conflicts. By watching verbal exchange and interplay among human beings belonging to one of a kind cultural systems, wherein implicit verbal exchange codes play a critical position in human interplay, Hall become one of the first researchers to factor out the difficulties encountered. He distinguishes 3 foremost additives which might be the important thing to recognize and to decipher the conduct of an come across or a foreigner. Hall considered "Culture hides much more than it reveals, and strangely enough, what it hides, it hides most effectively from its own participants" [23,53]. He defined non-verbal verbal exchange as "the silent language" that is unconscious and controls everyone. He had located super emphasis on time, area and context factors in intercultural verbal exchange. Hall argues that each tradition is stricken by the way where in, time, area and context are handles according to Byram. 1.1 The linguistic competence It is the ability to produce, interpret meaningful utterances and apply the rules of the language: (phonetic, phonological, morphological, syntactic, semantic codes etc.). It is the conventional meaning which native speakers would normally attach to an utterance when used in isolation. The structure of a language often reflects the important themes of culture. Thus, many languages distinguish a formal form and an informal form of address (you and tu in French, du and sie in German Sie, you and usted in Spanish etc), but

the difference lies in the contextual configurations that encourage people to choose a form rather than another, and the transition from the formal to the informal form is of a great difference from a language to another.

1.2 The discourse competence It is the ability to use appropriate strategies in the construction and interpretation of texts, or the ability to recognize different patterns of discourse, to connect sentences or utterances to an overall theme or topic and the ability to infer the meaning of large units of spoken written texts. In other words, it is the ability to understand and to produce certain types of speech.

1.3 The strategic competence It is the ability to compensate for imperfect knowledge of linguistic, sociolinguistic, and discourse rules or limiting factors in their application such as fatigue, distraction, or inattention. In other words, it is to find out some strategies or finding ways of getting our meaning across. It concerns the ability to use verbal and non-verbal strategies to achieve and maintain contact with the interlocutor and manage the act of communication in agreement with the speaker's intention to communicate. An important aspect is neglected is the strategy of the verbal turn -taking and interruption are not taken into consideration. In some cultures, the interlocutor has to show his interest by intervening before the other has completed his sentence (Latin cultures A and B). In other cultures, the interruption is seen as rude and unacceptable: it is expected that the person has completed his sentence before beginning to speak.

1.4 The sociolinguistic competence It is the awareness of ways or the ability to use the appropriate language to a given context, taking into account the roles of the participants, the setting.

Sociolinguistic competence covers the relation among linguistic alerts and their contextual or situational meaning.

1.5 The socio-cultural competence It is the expertise and "the appropriation" of social guidelines and norms of interaction among people and institutions, understanding of cultural records and the dating among social objects, in different words, it's far approximately the understanding of the interlocutor's tradition for example, his belief of time, his value's scale. Moreover,

variations bring about serious verbal exchange problems. The values that we take delivery of as being beautiful, right and right, and what does not.

Conclusion.

Moreover, learning language and culture should go together at all levels and one does not happen without the other. Intercultural competence cannot be learned without intercultural understanding which is based on the knowledge of culture above all, from linguistic competence to the communicative competence till achieving the intercultural communicative competence if the goal is really intercultural competence. Byram planned to build-up the intercultural communicative competence which is based on the concept of the ‘intercultural speaker’.

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